
A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF JUVENILE JUSTICE (CARE AND PROTECTION OF CHILDREN) ACT, 2015

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the significant legal reforms introduced on the recommendation of Justice Verma's Committee to protect women and children from exploitation, sexual assault, and violence. A key area of focus in these discussions has been 'juvenile delinquency,' which has become a critical issue within the realm of criminal law in India. The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000, was enacted to safeguard the rights of juveniles, outlining specific procedures for dealing with juveniles in conflict with the law. This legislation is guided by the principle that juveniles are the future of the individual and the nation, as they are considered the building blocks of society and carriers of humanity.

However, there are two sides to every coin. On one side, the innocence and lack of maturity associated with youth often raise concerns about their ability to make informed decisions. On the other side, some juvenile delinquents commit heinous crimes that are no less severe than those committed by adults, often in the most brutal forms. The Delhi gang rape case of 2012 and the Shakti Mills gang rape case are chilling examples. Recent statistics from the National Crime Record Bureau indicate a 60% increase in rape cases committed by juveniles between 2012 and 2013.

The primary objective of this paper is to explore whether the principles of Juvenile Justice conflict with the rights of victims and to investigate the underlying reasons why a juvenile might commit a "heinous crime." In response to this alarming trend, the Indian Parliament enacted the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015, which warrants a critical and careful analysis. This paper examines whether lowering the age of criminal responsibility might lead to retributive justice rather than reformatory and restorative justice. It also questions whether the age threshold for criminal liability should be reduced for serious crimes like rape and murder, from a judicial perspective. Additionally, this paper provides a comparative analysis of juvenile laws in different countries, focusing on the minimum age for criminal liability, and suggests solutions to enhance the effectiveness of the Juvenile Justice System and Juvenile Justice Delivery Mechanism in India.

Keywords - Juvenile delinquency, sexual assault, heinous crimes, Juvenile Justice

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I. Introduction

The new Act takes us back several decades, reminiscent of the 1920s. It claims to consolidate and amend the laws concerning children alleged or found to conflict with the law and children in need of care and protection (CNCP) by addressing their basic needs. However, this Act undermines the Constitution and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) by allowing children aged 16 to 18, accused of committing heinous offenses—those punishable by seven years or more of imprisonment—to be tried and sentenced as adults. This represents a significant regression in law-making, arguably one of the most backward steps in the history of child rights, setting us back even beyond what was available 150 years ago.

II. Brief History of the Legislation

The Apprentices Act of 1850 was the first piece of legislation addressing children in conflict with the law, allowing courts to treat children who committed petty offenses as apprentices rather than imprison them. The Reformatory School Act of 1897 was another significant piece of legislation from colonial times, providing that children under 15 sentenced to imprisonment could be sent to reformatory schools instead of prisons. Since then, the trend has been to expand the scope of juvenile justice laws and move away from punitive systems.

The three presidencies—Madras, Bengal, and Bombay—each enacted their own codified laws for children. The Madras Children Act of 1920 established a separate juvenile court and residential institutions to ensure children did not face the regular criminal justice system. Similarly, the Bengal and Bombay Children Acts of 1922 and 1924, though differing in the qualifying age for defining children, shared common features with other children's laws of the time. These laws aimed to dissociate children from the adult criminal justice system by establishing separate children's courts and residential institutions where children in conflict with the law could stay pending the conclusion of their proceedings or even after their cases were resolved.

Post-independence, in 1953, Parliament discussed a children's bill, which was later dropped due to the reorganization of states. On November 20, 1956, the United Nations General Assembly unanimously adopted the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, with India being a party to the declaration. In the same year, a children's bill was introduced in Parliament, eventually passed in 1960 as the first model central legislation on the subject. However, this law applied only to Union Territories, assuming that juvenile justice was a state matter under the Constitution.

The Child Act of 1960 established two separate adjudicatory bodies to deal with children in conflict with the law and children needing care and protection. It prohibited the imposition of the death penalty or imprisonment on children and barred their detention in jails or police stations. In 1974, India developed a National Policy for the Welfare of Children, and a year later, the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS), a child welfare scheme, was launched.

The Juvenile Justice Act of 1986, passed by Parliament, marked a significant step forward. It extended protections for boys below 16 years and girls below 18 years and provided for the establishment of advisory boards, children's funds, and the appointment of institutions. Between 1986 and 2000, global developments moved toward restorative justice, culminating in the adoption of the UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules) in 1985. In 1986, the Supreme Court of India, in the case of *Sheela Barse vs. Union of India*, ordered that a suitable juvenile justice system be enforced in all states.

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act of 2000, influenced by the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and global standards, marked a shift from the earlier discriminatory definitions of juveniles. It defined a child (whether a boy or girl) as anyone under 18 years of age, moving away from outdated and problematic terminology such as "delinquent juvenile" and "neglected juvenile." The Act aimed to advance the agenda of restorative justice and reformation.

However, the new Juvenile Justice Act, of 2015, represents a significant regression. It allows for juveniles aged 16 to 18 years who commit heinous crimes—those punishable by seven years or more of imprisonment—to be tried as adults. This Act disregards 150 years of progressive law-making in juvenile justice, violating several provisions of both national and international law. The Women and Child Development Ministry argued that time spent in reformation homes does not necessarily lead to behavioral correction, but it is unclear which developed societies have demonstrated a decrease in juvenile crime by subjecting adolescents to the adult criminal justice system. The experiences of the United States and Britain, which are considered developed societies, might offer some insight.

The new Act violates numerous provisions, including clauses 7, 15(3), 16(1), 19(3), 20, 21, 22, 25(1) and 25(2), and 102(2)(a) of the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015. It also contradicts various international conventions such as Articles 2, 6, 37(b), and 40(2)(a),(b)(i) of the UNCRC, as well as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The old juvenile justice system in India focused on rehabilitation, but the country is now adopting a retributive approach for heinous crimes committed by children aged 16 to 18.

The new Act lacks clarity on several key concepts, such as the definition of a "child," what constitutes a "heinous crime," and the meaning of "full contribution to society." The primary difference between the new Act and the old one is that the new Act leans toward retributive justice, while the old Act was rehabilitative. This shift violates constitutional and international provisions.

The main objective of the Act, as stated in its preamble, is to consolidate and amend the law relating to children alleged and found to conflict with the law and children in need of care and protection, by addressing their basic needs through proper care, protection, development, treatment, and social reintegration. It aims to adopt a child-friendly approach in the adjudication and disposal of matters in the best interests of children and to ensure their rehabilitation through the processes provided and the institutions and bodies established.

However, based on the Act's preamble, none of these objectives can be achieved by sending children alleged or found to conflict with the law to places of safety or the adult criminal justice system.

Transferring juveniles to adult prisons deprives them of protection and treatment, subjecting them to physical and sexual abuse by adult undertrials and convicts, and leaving them with no option but to pursue a life of crime. Additionally, the Act fails to clearly define key terms such as "child" and how to determine when a juvenile should be treated as an adult.

III. Definition of Child/Juvenile

The Children Act of 1960 introduced a sex-based definition of a child in the context of juvenile justice in India for the first time. It established 16 years as the appropriate cut-off age for juvenile justice, reflecting practices in other countries. According to Section 2(c) of the Act, a "child" was defined as a boy who had not attained the age of 16 years or a girl who had not attained the age of 18 years. The Act categorized children into two groups: neglected children and delinquent children.

In the Juvenile Justice Act (JJA) of 1986, the term "child" was not defined, and instead, the word "juvenile" was used. A "juvenile" was defined as a boy who had not attained the age of 16 years or a girl who had not attained the age of 18 years, mirroring the earlier definition of a child in the Children Act of 1960. The dictionary meaning of "juvenile" refers to someone physiologically immature or underdeveloped, with characteristics typically associated with children. The JJA adopted a similar sex-based definition of "juvenile" without further explanation.

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act of 2000 modified the age limit to 18 years, not due to any perceived unconstitutionality in the earlier definition but to align with the definition of a child under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). However, the new Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act of 2015 replaced the old Act and introduced significant changes.

In the U.K., a person under the age of 17 can be tried as an adult in cases of serious offenses, and a youth offender charged jointly with an adult is tried in a regular court. In the U.S., special juvenile courts handle cases involving individuals under 18, though approximately 20 states allow juveniles to be tried and sentenced as adults. In France, any person under 18 can only be tried by special juvenile courts, with separate courts established for serious offenses committed by minors aged 16-18, but not in adult courts.

In contrast, the new Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act of 2015 in India permits children aged 16 to 18 who are alleged to have committed heinous offenses to be tried and sentenced as adults, without the provision for separate courts as seen in France.

IV. Definition of Heinous offence

"Heinous offenses" are defined as those carrying a minimum punishment of seven years or more under the Indian Penal Code or any other prevailing law. In this context, heinous offenses are described as those warranting over seven years of imprisonment, including at least 46 offenses for which juveniles aged 16 to 18 could potentially be tried as adults. This extends beyond cases under the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, the Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances Act, the Maharashtra Control of Organised Crime Act, and the Prevention of Terrorism Act.

The new system implies that individuals found guilty of offenses carrying a mandatory minimum sentence will be subject to that sentence, undermining the principle of last resort recognized under the UNCRC. This rigid sentencing approach leaves judges with no option but to institutionalize the individual, potentially violating the prohibition against cruel, inhuman, and degrading treatment.

Clause 15 of the Act requires the Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) to assess whether a child accused of a heinous crime possesses the physical and mental capacity to commit the offense, as well as the circumstances surrounding the alleged crime. However, the individualized assessment of an adolescent's mental capacity is fraught with potential errors and arbitrariness, as it exceeds the limits of current scientific understanding. This flawed assessment process may allow inherent biases to influence decisions about which juveniles are transferred to adult courts, leading to violations of Articles 14 and 21 of the Indian Constitution. It also undermines the presumption of innocence, a cornerstone of both juvenile and criminal justice systems, as the JJB must make this decision before any evidence is presented.

This marks a significant departure from the JJB's previous role, which focused on ensuring the best interests of the juvenile. The Board is now tasked with the conflicting responsibility of determining which juvenile offenders should be processed through the adult criminal justice system. This shift is based on the misconception that juveniles are as culpable as adults.

India has made a serious error by replicating a failed Western model of retributive justice. The practice of transferring juveniles to adult jails, as proposed in the Act, has been in place in the United States for over two decades. The U.S. Centers for Disease Control's independent task force on community preventive services published scientific evidence evaluating the effectiveness of waiver laws. Their research, based on various scholarly studies, concluded that transfer policies generally lead to increased arrests for subsequent crimes, including violent offenses, among juveniles who were transferred compared to those retained in the juvenile justice system. The evidence suggests that these policies do more harm than good, contrary to their intended purpose of reducing violent or criminal behavior.

The UNCRC has stated that the minimum age of criminal responsibility should not be lower than 12 years, to increase it over time. India has failed in this regard, as its minimum age of criminal responsibility is set at seven years, significantly below the internationally prescribed standard of 12 years. The Act presented an opportunity to provide clarity on this issue, but it has fallen short of doing so.

And also it violates the various provisions as following:

V. Violations of the Indian Constitution

1. The assumptions in clauses 7, 15(3), 16(1), 19(3), 20, 21, and 22, which equate the culpability of children aged 16 to 18 years with that of adults and deem them competent to stand trial in adult courts, violate the right to equality under Article 14 and the special protections afforded to children under Article 15(3).

2. The preliminary inquiry conducted by the Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) under clause 16(1) infringes upon the constitutional prohibition against procedural arbitrariness, as outlined in Articles 14 and 21.
3. The inherent arbitrariness in the assessment of a child's potential for reformation by the Children's Court, as stipulated in clause 21, violates the requirement for procedural fairness under Article 21.
4. Clause 7 contravenes the constitutional prohibition under Article 20(1) against the retrospective application of penal laws and penalties.

VI. Violations of Rights under the Juvenile Justice Law

1. The preliminary inquiry conducted by the Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) under clause 16(1) undermines the presumption of innocence.
2. The exclusion of children aged 16 to 18 years who have committed heinous offences under clause 19(1) denies them access to rehabilitative alternatives provided under the JJ Act 2015.
3. Institutionalization under clauses 20(3), 21(2), and 22 becomes the only option rather than a measure of last resort for children in this category, violating the fundamental principles of the child's best interest and the use of institutionalization as a last resort.
4. The transfer of children to adult courts under clause 19(3) deprives them of the right to be handled by a child-friendly, multidisciplinary Juvenile Justice Board, infringes upon their right to privacy, and violates the principle of the child's best interest as established under the JJ Act 2000, Model Rules 2007, and the JJ Act 2015.
5. The maintenance of records for a child transferred to jail under clause 25(3) violates the principle of a fresh start, obstructs the goal of rehabilitation, and exposes the child to potential legal disqualifications.

VII. Violation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989

1. Subjecting children aged 16 to 18 years to trial and punishment as adults contravenes the prohibition on discrimination under Article 2.
2. The transfer system undermines the core principle that the best interest of the child should be a primary consideration, as mandated by Article 3.
3. Institutionalization under clauses 20(3), 21(2), and 22 breaches the fundamental right that deprivation of liberty should be a measure of last resort and for the shortest appropriate time, in violation of Articles 6 and 37(b).

4. The preliminary inquiry conducted by the Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) under clause 16(1) infringes upon the presumption of innocence guaranteed by Article 40(2)(b)(i).
5. Both the preliminary inquiry by the JJB under clause 16(1) and the determination by the Children's Court under clause 21(1) violate the prohibition against arbitrary deprivation of liberty, as outlined in Article 37(b).
6. Trial and sentencing of children in an adult court violate the obligation under Article 40(1) to ensure that the child is treated with dignity and that their reintegration into society is facilitated.
7. The transfer of children to prison under clauses 20(3) and 21(2)(ii) contravenes the mandatory requirement of separating children from adults, as stipulated in Article 37(c).
8. Clause 7 violates the prohibition on retroactive application of juvenile justice under Article 40(2)(a).
9. The maintenance of records for a child transferred to jail under clause 25(3) infringes upon the right to privacy throughout all stages of the proceedings, as protected by Article 40(2)(vii).

These provisions are in clear violation.

VIII. International Standards on Juvenile Justice & Serious Offences

Concluding Observations of the Committee on Rights of the Child: India (2000)

- "...ensure that persons under 18 years are not tried as adults."; "ensure that boys under 18 years are covered by the definition of juvenile, as girls already are."

Concluding Observations of the Committee on Rights of the Child: India (2004)

- "...deeply concerned that the POTA allows for the prosecution of children by special courts and that the procedure used in these cases does not respect articles 37, 40 and 39 of the Convention."

General Comment No. 10 on Children's rights in juvenile justice. (2007)

- "States parties which limit the applicability of their juvenile justice rules to children under the age of 16 (or lower) years, or which allow by way of exception that 16 or 17-year-old children are treated as adult criminals, change their laws to achieve a nondiscriminatory full application of their juvenile justice rules to all persons under the age of 18 years."

Concluding Observations of the Committee on Rights of the Child: India (2014)

- Give effect to the Juvenile Justice Rules of 2007 establishing the minimum age of criminal responsibility at 18 and maintain it at an internationally acceptable level” and “In cases where detention is necessary, ensure age-appropriate separation of children in Observation and Special Homes and that children in conflict with the law are not detained together with children in need of protection or with adults and that detention conditions are compliant with international standards, including concerning access to education and health services.”

The committee made some important recommendations:

➤ Committee on the Rights of the Child has made recommendations to:

➤ 30 State Parties to abolish life imprisonment for child offenders.

➤ 50 State Parties to stop treating juveniles as adults and to amend their laws to ensure that all children are dealt with under the juvenile justice system.

➤ 106 State Parties to ensure the separation of juveniles from adults during detention

- The UN Human Rights Council has also called on States to ensure that legislation and practices do not permit life imprisonment for offenses committed by persons under 18 years of age in two separate resolutions and the UN General Assembly has encouraged States to consider repealing all forms of life imprisonment including life imprisonment “with the possibility of release for offenses committed by persons under 18”.
- In January 2013, concern was expressed about the continued detention of child soldiers by the US in detention facilities in Iraq & Afghanistan. The US was urged to ensure that “all children under the age of 18 be handled by the juvenile justice system in all circumstances and presume young persons to be children if in doubt regarding their age.

A significant portion of rape and kidnapping cases involves situations categorized as "love" cases or consensual elopement. A recent analysis by *The Hindu* of 600 sexual assault cases before the Delhi District Courts found that “Of the cases fully tried, over 40% involved consensual sex, typically involving the elopement of a young couple, where the girl’s parents later charged the boy with rape. An additional 25% of cases pertained to "breach of promise to marry.”

- Under the POCSO Act, children involved in such cases may be viewed as status offenders.
- Data on juveniles apprehended for consensual sex under the POCSO Act and IPC is currently unavailable.

IX. Implication of preliminary inquiry on rights of juveniles

Numerous instances of children being wrongfully apprehended by the police cannot be overlooked. The Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) is required to assess whether a child possesses the physical and mental capacity to commit the alleged offense, along with considering the 'circumstances in which the offense was committed.' This assessment implies an assumption that the child has already committed the alleged offense. The JJB is tasked with arbitrarily determining culpability before even a prima facie case is established. Assessing 'mental capacity' is an exceptionally complex process and will inevitably result in arbitrary transfers. Even with the assistance of experienced psychologists, the JJB cannot accurately carry out this assessment.

Implications of being tried as an adult:

Transferring children above 16 years of age who are alleged to have committed a heinous offense will strip them of their right to equality and protections under the Juvenile Justice system. This action violates the principles of acting in the child's best interest and the standard that institutionalization should only be used as a last resort. The question arises: Are individuals between 16 and 18 years old truly competent to stand trial as adults? Subjecting juveniles to the adult criminal justice system demands that they make decisions as adults, despite not being fully equipped to comprehend the risks and consequences. Additionally, due to their cognitive limitations, juveniles have a reduced capacity to assist their legal counsel and may not receive a fair trial. In the United States, it has been observed that such cognitive deficits hinder the juvenile's ability to navigate the complexities of adult court proceedings effectively. It's important to note that Children's Courts were originally established to try offenses committed against children, not offenses committed by children.

Arbitrariness inherent in any assessment of reformation:

Determining whether a person has "undergone reformatory changes" or "can be a contributing member of society" is inherently subjective and susceptible to arbitrariness, especially given the inconsistent quality of rehabilitative services that the State is obligated to provide under the new Act. The child in question is not subjected to the same rigorous evaluation. This approach is likely to lead to the disproportionate targeting of marginalized communities in India. Data already indicates that over half of the children apprehended for offenses come from families with an annual income of less than Rs. 25,000, while only 0.55% of apprehended children come from families with an annual income exceeding Rs. 3,00,000. There is little doubt that the provisions of the current Bill will result in class, caste, and religion-based targeting of children, under the guise of assessing their potential societal contribution and extent of reformation.

Place of Safety:

Individuals between 18-21 years who are apprehended for committing an offense before they turned 18, and are denied bail, along with children under 16 whose behavior makes it unsafe for them or others to be housed in a Special Home, as well as those between 16-21 years accused or convicted of heinous offenses, are subject to segregation. The state government is mandated to establish at least one "place of safety" in the state.

The proposed provision regresses legislative progress and undermines constitutional protections by allowing children to be tried and sentenced as adults for offenses committed during childhood. This

violates the right to equality under Article 14 by creating an arbitrary distinction between individuals apprehended before 21 years of age and those apprehended after. This differentiation lacks a rational basis and also violates Article 15(1) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which enshrines non-derogable rights. Furthermore, it broadens the scope of transfer provisions in the Bill to include not only heinous offenses but also serious offenses, mandating adult trials.

The new juvenile act is a regressive step that reintroduces the outdated notion of convicting children as adult criminals, effectively reverting to 19th-century practices. The selective system, where the Juvenile Justice Board (JJB) has discretionary power to transfer children aged 16 to 18 accused of serious crimes to the adult criminal justice system, contradicts the entire objective and principles of juvenile justice.

According to the Verma Committee, before holding a child responsible for a crime, the state must first ensure the provision of basic constitutional rights. The provisions under Clauses 16 and 19(3) are not only controversial but also violate fundamental rights granted by the Constitution, conflicting with the very purpose of the juvenile justice system. A U.S. study found that 80% of juveniles released from adult prisons go on to commit more offenses, highlighting the failure of this punitive approach.

In a country with 472 million children, only 1.2% are involved in criminal activities. This act disproportionately affects marginalized groups such as OBCs, SCs, STs, poor people, and minorities. Most children in conflict with the law come from poor families—77.5% of children apprehended in 2013 came from households with a monthly income of less than Rs. 4,000. Additionally, 85% of these children did not receive higher or secondary education. The selective and unequal treatment of children under this act violates fundamental rights under Articles 14, 15(3), and 21.

Clause 7 of the new Act contradicts Article 21's right to equality, violates the principles of procedural fairness under Articles 14 and 21, and conflicts with the test of fairness in Article 21 by allowing only one month for the JJB to conduct a preliminary inquiry. This short time frame essentially presumes guilt, which is unconstitutional. The act also violates the Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (1985) and lacks specific provisions for female juveniles or sex offenders. Moreover, it does not establish effective monitoring and coordination mechanisms.

In conclusion, children under 18 must be protected from the adult criminal justice system. They require care, education, and counseling, not punitive measures. The state should focus on rehabilitating and reintegrating these children into society rather than subjecting them to retributive justice. We must protect and rescue children, not destroy their future.

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